

Enterprise GIS (Geographical Information Systems) with SAP HANA – Are we taking advantage of Location Analytics

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Introduction

Location data is becoming part of the enterprise operations on a day-to-day basis. Geospatial Technology helps maximize the profits for industries and improves decision-making for governments by analyzing and managing complex datasets. In Intelligence Enterprise IoT, LiDAR & Drone data will be the primary source for handling the industry-based applications. Specifically, satellite data is used to predict the disaster/climate to avoid unexpected business losses. This article focuses on the concept & applications of Enterprise GIS with present market tools to integrate with the SAP Platform.

Enterprise GIS

Before discussing the Applications, it is necessary to understand the Enterprise GIS – Which is the implementation of geospatial infrastructure, processes, and tools to integrate business requirements within the organization and scale for future demands. In the last decade GIS Systems have become very stable and matured with capable of decentralizing business operations but when comes to the integration the customer might face the following issues

- data duplication

able to integrate across the platforms without interoperability & compatibility issues. The company should plan the Enterprise GIS as financially viable and technically sound to handle data standardization & acquisition, and application development by managing the right infrastructure Commonly the plan should consist.

1. Design specifications of Enterprise GIS including data, product & maintenance
2. System, Application & Database Architecture with Functional Specification document
3. Implementation plan with tasks, schedule, and activities with organizational responsibilities.

Figure 1: From Data to Application. Source: esri.com

The image will explain the common infrastructure of a GIS process. The initial step will start with the standardization of the data acquisition and database handling. Data store helps to handle the high volume of data with real-time observational data. The data will vary based on the customer needs and application area. Hosting server and Portal helps developers/customers to access data store based on the level of access defined by the administrator.

Enterprise GIS Applications

Enterprise GIS is adopted by different sectors; The potential of the applications is tremendous in the smart devices era. The following applications & their use cases will give an outline of how to take advantage of location analytics. The most beneficial industry is the utility industry like telecom, gas, water & electricity which plays a significant impact on economic & social development.

TYPE	LIBRARIES / SOFTWARE
Desktop GIS	ArcGIS Pro, QGIS, gvSIG, MapInfo, ERDAS IMAGINE, Global Mapper
Database	ESRI Geodatabase, SAP HANA DB, Oracle, PostGIS
Web Mapping	ArcGIS JavaScript API, Open Layers, Leaflet, Cesium
GIS Server	ArcGIS Server, GeoServer, MapServer
Data Store	ArcGIS Data Store, PostgreSQL
Core Libraries	GDAL/OGR, GeoTools, GEOS, PROJ4

Image 1: Top-rated tools in the market to Implement Enterprise GIS

SAP with ESRI

ArcGIS Enterprise is now supporting SAP HANA Cloud to maximize the full power of the geospatial platform. Many organizations deal with multiple sources of unconnected data. They need a central repository to unify their databases and provide a complete overview of all their data. Esri and SAP are both dedicated to enabling digital transformations with the seamless integration of operational and locational data, both are accelerating

Figure 2 : ArcGIS Enterprise Integration with SAP Source: esri.com

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Check out the PM360 app here [Mobolutions PM360](#). If you have questions on SAP with ESRI Integration or want to know more about it, do not hesitate to reach out to us at [Praveenkumar](#) / [Bharath](#) / [Gobinath](#) or schedule a quick meet :- [click here](#).

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